

Well-Connectedness and Community Detection

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Abstract

Community detection approaches help reveal the meso-scale structure of complex networks. Integral to the problem of community detection is the expectation that communities are edge-dense and “well-connected”. Surprisingly, we find that five different community detection methods—the Leiden algorithm optimizing the Constant Potts Model, the Leiden algorithm optimizing modularity, Infomap, Markov Clustering (MCL), and Iterative k-core (IKC)—produce clusters that fail even a mild requirement for well-connectedness. To address this issue, we have developed the Connectivity Modifier (CM), which iteratively removes small edge cuts and re-clusters until all communities detected are well-connected according to a user-specified criterion. A reduction in node coverage is seen when CM post-processes the output of these community detection methods applied to real-world networks (ranging in size from approximately 35,000 to 75,000,000 nodes). Results on synthetic networks show that the CM algorithm generally maintains or improves accuracy in recovering true communities. Our study also underscores the importance of network clusterability—the fraction of a network that exhibits community structure—and the need for more models of community structure where networks contain nodes that are not assigned to communities. In summary, we address well-connectedness as an important aspect of clustering and provide CM, a scalable open-source tool, to ensure that clusters are well-connected.

Author summary

Community detection – a term interchangeable with clustering – is used in many analyses of networks. An expectation is that such communities, clusters, or groups are dense and well-connected. However, density is separable from well-connectedness, as clusters may be dense without being well-connected. Our study demonstrates that several clustering algorithms generate clusters that are not well-connected, using a mild standard we propose. To address this issue, we provide the Connectivity Modifier (CM), an open source tool to allow users to specify well-connectedness and enforce it in the output of multiple community detection methods.

Introduction

Graph clustering, also known as community detection, is integral to network analysis and has many applications [1, 2]. In graph clustering, the vertices of the input network are partitioned into disjoint sets, with the object of having each subset display greater cohesion, so that the subsets represent communities [3–5].

There are many approaches to defining communities in graphs, and many have been based on finding subsets of nodes that display greater density than the background density [6, 7]. However, another notion that is relevant to defining a community is that it is well-connected, meaning that the number of edges needed to remove in order to disconnect the set is not too small [8]. While the two concepts seem related, it is possible for a cluster to be dense, relative to the background, without being well-connected; an example is a graph with two cliques connected by a single edge, inside a relatively sparse network [9]. Thus, density is a desirable property of communities, but by itself it does not ensure well-connectedness, leading to the possibility that clusters produced by methods designed to ensure dense clusters may not be well-connected. We emphasize this point by saying *edge density and well-connectedness are expected but separable properties of communities*.

Related to well-connectedness is the concept of “resolution-limit”, which says that a clustering method may not be able to return communities that are too small, and will instead merge them into larger clusters. A prime example of this is the case of a ring of cliques, where some methods may return pairs of cliques rather than the individual cliques [10]. That modularity optimization was subject to this resolution limit was established in [10], with the result that other methods, such as optimizing under the Constant Potts Model [8], were developed to address this limitation. Also related to well-connectedness is the observation that some methods for searching for optimal clusterings may not be guaranteed to produce connected clusters; this issue was observed for the Louvain software [11] algorithm, and led to the Leiden [8] algorithm, which does have the guarantee of producing connected clusters.

Despite these advances, not much is understood about how well-connected the clusters are that are produced by different clustering methods. Of the commonly used methods, to the best of our knowledge, only optimizing under the Constant Potts Model (CPM) [12] provides any guarantee for well-connectedness. Specifically, as established in [8], if a cluster C is in an optimal CPM-clustering with resolution parameter r , and if X is a set of edges whose removal splits C into A and $C \setminus A$, then the number of edges in X must be at least $r \times |A| \times |C \setminus A|$.

This lower bound is maximized when the edge cut splits a cluster into two components of approximately equal size, but is weaker when it produces an unbalanced split and minimized when the cut separates a single node from the remaining nodes in the cluster. Importantly, the bound depends on r , and small values of r produce weak bounds. It is also important to note that this guarantee applies to CPM-optimal clusterings but not to heuristics.

In this study, we evaluate five different clustering methods with respect to how well-connected their clusters are. We explore the Leiden algorithm [8], optimizing either modularity or CPM. We also study Infomap [13], Markov clustering (MCL) [14], and the Iterative k-core (IKC) method [15]. Using seven real world networks that range from roughly 34,000 nodes to 75 million nodes, we find, according to a modest requirement we enforce, that each method produces clusters that are not well connected (though the degree depends on the method and the network), and that some methods even produce disconnected clusters.

In order to address this problem, we have developed, in open-source software, the Connectivity Modifier (CM) [16, 17, 21]. This method is used in conjunction with a specified clustering method, such as Leiden, and ensures that the clustering that is

produced is well-connected. CM uses a natural algorithmic approach: given the clustering of the network, it computes – for each cluster in the clustering – a minimum edge cut (“min cut”). If that edge cut is too small (i.e., below a size defined by the user), then the edge cut is deleted from the cluster, thus breaking the cluster into two subsets of vertices. These subsets are then re-clustered using the specified clustering method, and the process repeats until all the clusters are considered well-connected. Of note here, CM allows the user to specify a function of the cluster size for the lower bound; this allows the user to either enforce greater or lesser well-connectedness.

Using CM with these clustering methods on seven real-world networks, we demonstrate the insights that CM can provide into community structure in networks. Additional analyses on synthetic networks provide evidence that CM improves community detection accuracy under many conditions.

We now build on previous results from earlier versions of CM [16,21] that provided support for the Leiden and IKC software. The current version [18] also provides support for MCL and Infomap, and is being extended to integrate other clustering methods. In our earlier article [17], we described CM and provided evidence that Leiden (optimizing both modularity and CPM), IKC, Infomap, and MCL all produced clusters that were poorly connected, according to a mild requirement for the size of the minimum cut; further, we explored the impact of CM on Leiden and IKC on both empirical and synthetic networks. New observations in this study, extending the work we presented in [17], include evaluation of the impact of CM on the Infomap and MCL methods, detailed investigation into the impact of CM on clustering outputs from IKC and Leiden optimizing modularity or CPM, and additional observations using synthetic networks.

Our study reveals that all clustering methods we tested have a tendency to produce clusters that are not well-connected, but this tendency is more pronounced in some clustering methods, suggesting that some commonly used methods may over-cluster. We also see that CM can be used to modify the input clustering, ensuring that all output clusters are well-connected and above the minimum size (both as specified by the user). Thus, CM provides one way to address the challenge of providing well-connected clusters, while also utilizing a selected clustering approach (e.g., modularity or CPM). This study thus provides both an initial step towards addressing the objective of producing well-connected and dense clusters, while also raising new questions. For example, our study can be seen as challenging the assumption that all the vertices in every network should be in a community, and suggests instead that in some cases, only a subset of a real world network will exhibit community structure and “clusterability” at the network level [19]. Thus, users of community detection methods should evaluate the clusters they find for well-connectedness, before making inferences about community structure in their network. From a theoretical perspective, our study suggests that mathematical models of networks and communities, as well as optimization problems for community detection in networks, should consider well-connectedness along with the realization that for some networks, it may be that not every node in the network is in a community.

Results and Discussion

We are specifically interested in identifying groups of articles, taken from the scientific literature, and thus are focused on clustering methods that can be used on large citation networks [8,15]. Results shown here are based on seven real-world networks (Table 2) and 34 synthetic networks (Materials and Methods). The real-world networks ranged from 34,546 nodes to 75,025,194 nodes, and the synthetic networks were constructed using Leiden clusterings of these networks. Leiden and IKC completed on all networks, but Infomap failed on the largest network, and MCL returned output only from the

smallest network (cit_hepph) we analyzed.

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Initial Observations

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Examining minimum cut sizes

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In an initial exploration of a 75,025,194 node network we constructed (Materials and Methods) from Open Citations data [20], we computed the min cut of all clusters generated using the Leiden algorithm optimizing either CPM or modularity (Fig. 1). For CPM, we used five different resolution parameter values (r , drawn from 0.5, 0.1, 0.01, 0.001, 0.0001). Designating very small clusters as not being of practical interest, unless otherwise specified, we report node coverage throughout this manuscript as the percentage of nodes in clusters of size at least 11.

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(a) Min-cut size distribution for different Leiden clusterings (b) Min-cut sizes as a function of the cluster size

Fig 1. Minimum edge cut sizes and node coverage of Leiden clusters (using CPM and modularity) on the Open Citations network. For each subfigure, we show results for clustering using Leiden under CPM optimization with five different resolution values and modularity. In (a) we show the box plot of min cut sizes found across all clusters for a given clustering, with blue text indicating the node coverage for that clustering (i.e., percentage of nodes in the input network found in clusters of size at least 11). In (b) we show the cut sizes as a function of the cluster size. Note that except for CPM-clustering with very large resolution values ($r = 0.1$ or $r = 0.5$), most clusters have edge cuts of size 1, and that CPM-clustering with the high resolution values and modularity clustering have low node coverage (below 50%). We also see that the size of the minimum edge cut increases with cluster size for CPM-optimization, but this is not the case for modularity-optimization.

For Leiden-CPM clusterings (Fig. 1), we see that as the resolution value is decreased, (i) node coverage increases from 6% to 99%, (ii) the frequency of small mincuts increases, and (iii) cluster sizes increase. With respect to these measurements, clustering under modularity is most similar to clustering under CPM at the lowest resolution value used. Strikingly, optimizing under modularity had the highest node coverage (99.4%) but 98.7% of its 2,184 clusters had a minimum edge cut size of 1, that is, they could be split by removing a single edge. Additionally, where node coverage is high, clusters tend to be larger and fewer. We also observe that as the resolution value decreases from 0.5 down to 0.0001, the maximum size of any cluster increases for CPM-optimization. These data illustrate a tradeoff that users make with the Leiden algorithm optimizing

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CPM between small clusters, lower node coverage, and a reduced tendency for clusters to have small min cuts (achieved using CPM-optimization with larger resolution values) versus larger clusters, higher node coverage, and higher frequency of clusters with small min cuts (CPM-optimization with small resolution values or modularity-optimization).

In addition to the Open Citations network, we clustered six more networks (Materials and Methods), ranging in size from 34,546 nodes to 13,989,436 nodes using Leiden, IKC, Infomap, and MCL. Only Leiden and IKC ran to completion on all seven networks. Infomap ran on all but the Open Citations Network. MCL completed only on the smallest network (cit_hepph) we analyzed. IKC, the most conservative of the methods, did not return any clusters from the sparse wiki_talk network. Interestingly, while neither Leiden nor IKC generated disconnected clusters, Infomap generated disconnected clusters for some networks, maximized at 75% for the orkut network, and 7.2% of MCL clusters on the cit_hepph network were disconnected. These observations describe the prevalence of clusters that are not well-connected, with the extent dependent on clustering method and network.

Defining well-connected clusters

In a second exploratory experiment, we explored ways of defining “well-connected” or its negation, “poorly-connected”. While the existence of a small edge cut for a cluster intuitively signals poorly-connected, there are different ways of formalizing how small the cut must be for the cluster to be considered poorly connected. For the purposes of this study, we offer a definition that we then use to evaluate clusters. Briefly, we consider functions $B(n)$, with the interpretation being that if a cluster with n nodes has an edge cut of size $B(n)$ or smaller, then the cluster will be considered poorly connected. We want this bound to be modest, so that we do not label clusters as poorly connected too readily. Thus, we want $B(n)$ to grow very slowly so that it serves as a mild bound. We also want $B(n) \geq 1$ for all n that are large enough for the cluster to be considered a potential community.

Traag et al. [8], proved that if X is an edge cut for a cluster C in a CPM-optimal clustering (with resolution parameter r), whose removal splits C into two sets A and B , then $|X| \geq r \times |A| \times |B|$. Thus, the function $a(r, A, B) = r \times |A| \times |B|$ is a lower bound on the size of the minimum cut for any cluster in a CPM-optimal clustering. This function is maximized when $|A| = |B|$ and minimized when $|A| = 1$ and $|B| = n - 1$, where C has n nodes. Therefore, the minimum cut for any cluster with n nodes has size at least $r \times (n - 1)$. For example, when $r = 0.01$ and $n = 50$, then writing $t(n) = 0.01(n - 1)$ yields the lower bound on the size of the minimum cut in a CPM-optimal clustering with resolution parameter $r = 0.01$. Note that $0 < t(50) < 1$, and so this bound only establishes that the minimum edge cut is at least 1, which therefore simply asserts that the cluster is connected. In other words, for resolution values such as $r = 0.01$, the lower bound given in [8] is not particularly significant, and the bound is even weaker when the resolution value is smaller.

We seek lower bounds on the size of the minimum edge cut that are larger than $t(n) = 0.01 \times (n - 1)$ (the bound when $r = 0.01$) for small values of n but grow very slowly, and so do not exceed the $t(n)$ bound for large values of n .

We consider three functions: $f(n) = \log_{10} n$, $g(n) = \log_2 n$, and $h(n) = \frac{\sqrt{n}}{5}$; note that each of $f(n)$, $g(n)$ and $h(n)$ is strictly positive and increasing. The comparison between these functions in the range of cluster sizes $1 \leq n \leq 2000$ is shown in Fig. 2. As desired, for large enough n , $t(n)$ dominates the other functions, thus imposing a much stronger guarantee on the minimum cut size for the cluster. We also note that $f(n) < g(n)$ for all $n > 1$, but that the relationship between $f(n)$, $h(n)$, and $t(n)$ depends on n . For large n , however, $f(n)$ is less than all the other functions, making it the most slowly growing function.

Fig 2. Comparison of the lower bounds on edge cut sizes for defining well-connected clusters. (x-axis: n , y-axis: function value.) Here we compare four functions; $t(n) = 0.01(n - 1)$, $f(n) = \log_{10} n$, $g(n) = \log_2 n$, and $h(n) = \frac{\sqrt{n}}{5}$. By [8], $t(n)$ provides a guaranteed lower bound on the edge cut size that splits one node from the remaining nodes for a cluster with n nodes in an optimal CPM clustering, when $r = 0.01$. Also, $t(n)$ is the largest of the functions when $n > 1000$ and $f(n)$ is the smallest of the functions when $n > 239$. Thus, in general $t(n)$ is the strongest guarantee of the functions we compare when n is large, but the other functions provide somewhat stronger guarantees for the smaller values of n . In particular, for $n \leq 238$, $f(n) \geq t(n)$, so that $f(n)$ provides a stronger guarantee on these small- to moderate-sized clusters than $t(n)$.

Based on this comparison, we use $f(n) = \log_{10}(n)$ to define when a cluster of n nodes is well-connected: if the min cut size for the cluster is strictly greater than $\log_{10}(n)$ then we consider it well-connected, and otherwise we say that the cluster is poorly connected. Note that if we had picked $g(n)$ instead, we would have considered more clusters poorly connected, since $f(n) < g(n)$ for all n . Similarly, picking $h(n)$ would have generally been more stringent a requirement (at least for all but very small values of n), and so would have ruled more clusters as being poorly connected. Thus, $f(n) = \log_{10} n$ represents a very modest constraint on the size of the min cut for a cluster, in order for it to qualify as being well-connected.

Frequency of well-connected clusters

Our third exploratory experiment evaluated the frequency with which each of the clustering methods produced well-connected clusters. We used all clustering methods (i.e., Leiden optimizing either modularity or CPM, IKC, Infomap, and MCL) on all seven networks (Materials and Methods). Leiden and IKC completed on all networks, Infomap failed on the largest network, and MCL returned output only from the smallest network (cit_hepph) we analyzed. For those methods that completed on a given network, we calculated the percentage of the clusters that were well-connected, according to the threshold $f(n) = \log_{10} n$. Although all clustering methods generated some clusters that were not well-connected, some methods generated poorly connected clusters more often than others.

Results for Leiden used with either modularity or CPM are shown in Fig. 3(a), and

(a) Leiden CPM & Modularity **(b) IKC, Infomap, MCL**
Fig 3. Percentage of well-connected clusters in seven real-world networks ranging from 34,546 to 75M nodes. Panel (a) shows results for Leiden optimizing CPM at different resolution values and Leiden optimizing modularity, and panel (b) shows results for IKC, Infomap, and MCL. IKC did not return any clusters from the wiki_talk network. Infomap completed on all but Open Citations. MCL completed only on cit_hepph. Leiden and IKC ran to completion on all seven networks.

results for IKC, Infomap, and MCL are shown in Fig. 3(b). One important observation is that the resolution value for CPM-optimization within Leiden had a large impact on the frequency of poorly connected clusters, with only large resolution values (i.e., $r = 0.1$ or 0.5) mainly producing well-connected clusters. Small resolution values, on the other hand, produced many poorly connected clusters, including clusters that are trees (supplementary materials). Most IKC clusters were well-connected, ranging from 85.9% to 94% of the total number of clusters. Infomap produced well-connected clusters, varying from 5% (orkut) to 92.4% (cit_patents). MCL ran only on the cit_hepph network, where 81.3% of its clusters were well-connected.

Connectivity Modifier

We designed the Connectivity Modifier (CM) [16, 21] to modify outputs of clustering methods in order to ensure that all clusters are well-connected, according to the specified threshold provided by the user. CM can currently be used with four different clustering methods: Leiden (optimizing modularity or CPM), IKC, Infomap, and MCL. A parallelized version of CM has since been developed [18].

Here we describe the CM pipeline in a schematic (Fig. 4). The algorithm depends on three parameters that the user may specify (or use the default settings): (i) the clustering method, (ii) $f(n)$ (the lower bound on the size of a min cut), and (iii) B , the minimum allowed size of a cluster. In our study we explored CM with the default settings as follows: $f(n) = \log_{10}(n)$ and $B = 11$. In order to speed up the analysis, we include a pre-processing (filtering) step, which discards clusters that are trees (and so not well-connected) or of size less than B . Each cluster is then processed by CM, independently. First, the cluster is checked using VieCut [22] to see if it contains an edge cut of size at most $f(n)$; if so, the edge cut is removed, thus producing two subsets of nodes, which are each then re-clustered using the specified clustering method. This process repeats until the current iteration produces no change. At the end, all clusters are well-connected, but some may be below the allowed threshold: those are removed in

Fig 4. Connectivity Modifier Pipeline Schematic. The four-stage pipeline depends on user-specified algorithmic parameters: B (default 11), the minimum allowed size of a cluster, and $f(n)$ (default $\log_{10}(n)$), a bound on the minimum edge cut size for a cluster with n nodes, and clustering method. *Stage 1*: a clustering is computed. *Stage 2*: clusters are pre-processed by removing trees and those clusters of size less than B . *Stage 3*: the CM is applied to each cluster, removing edge cuts of sizes at most $f(n)$, reclustering, and recursing on clusters. *Stage 4*: clusters are post-processed by removing those of size less than B .

a final post-processing step.

Effect of CM on Clustered Real World Networks

Having demonstrated that all the clustering methods we study return poorly connected clusters under some conditions, we now examine the impact of using CM. Because our interest is mainly in methods that can scale to large networks (which MCL did not) and that do not tend to produce disconnected clusters (which Infomap does), our main focus in this section is on the the impact of CM on Leiden and IKC. However, we also provide an examination of the impact of CM on MCL and Infomap, although for these two methods our discussion is limited to just the node coverage.

Impact of CM on Leiden optimizing modularity or CPM

We examined two aspects of the impact of CM on Leiden clustering, optimizing both modularity and CPM using five different resolution parameter values. The first examines how node coverage drops as a result of the initial reduction (removing small clusters and trees) and after the full pipeline (i.e., post-CM). Results for this experiment (Fig. 5) show that initial node coverage depends on whether modularity or CPM is optimized, and for CPM it also depends on the resolution parameter. However, for both networks, node coverage drops after CM-processing, with maximum post-CM node coverage being 24.6% for the CEN and 68.7% for Open Citations, across all six conditions tested. The use of Leiden for CPM-optimization with the largest resolution value ($r = 0.5$) produced the smallest node coverage, both before CM-processing and after, while using one of the two smallest resolution values ($r = 0.0001$ or $r = 0.001$) achieved the largest node coverage, also before and after CM-processing. Optimizing modularity instead of CPM produced results very similar to CPM-optimization with the smallest resolution parameter. The impact of pre-processing is large for the two larger resolution values, but decreases with resolution value. It is interesting therefore to note that the second main step of the CM pipeline (iteratively looking for small cuts in clusters, removing them, and reclustering) has only a small impact on node coverage when the resolution parameter value is large, but the impact increases as the resolution

(a) Open Citations

(b) CEN

Fig 5. Reduction in node coverage after CM treatment of Leiden clusters. Subfigure (a) shows results for Open Citations and (b) shows results for the CEN. In each subfigure, green bars denote node coverage (percentage of nodes in clusters of size at least 2) in the input clustering, orange bars denote the percentage of nodes in clusters of size at least 2 after trees and clusters of size at most 10 are removed, and blue bars denote node coverage in the final output by CM. The Open Citations and CEN networks were clustered using the Leiden algorithm optimizing either modularity or CPM, with five different resolution values.

parameter value decreases.

To provide a detailed insight into the impact of CM on clusterings, we examined each cluster to see whether it was modified at all by CM, and if it was, whether it was reduced in size but remained a single cluster, or whether it was split into exactly two clusters, or into at least three clusters, or replaced entirely by singleton clusters (which is what happens when it is replaced by a collection of clusters that are all below the minimum size requirement, B). We refer to clusters that are not modified as *extant*, clusters that are made smaller but remain a single cluster as *reduced*, clusters that are split into exactly two clusters as *split*, and the remaining clusters that are replaced by a collection of singletons as *degraded*. The interpretation of these classifications is as follows. An extant cluster is one that was not modified by CM, and is regarded as valid. The reduced clusters are those that remain a single, but smaller, cluster after CM treatment, indicating that the set contained—as a proper subset—a single valid community. Those clusters that are split contain two or more valid clusters, suggesting the “resolution limit” reported for modularity in [10]. Finally, those clusters that are degraded, and so replaced by either a collection of singletons or clusters of size at most 10, are those that are considered to not contain any valid communities.

As seen in Fig. 6, when using Leiden optimizing CPM with resolution values $r \geq 0.1$, most produced clusters are extant. Hence, CPM optimization with resolution values at least 0.1 is not particularly affected by CM, indicating that many of the clusters are well-connected and above the minimum threshold for size (as otherwise, the clusters would be changed by CM). However, as seen in the previous figure, CPM optimization using these large resolution values also has small node coverage, indicating that this trend is likely due to the conservative nature of CPM clustering with large resolution values.

Also shown in Fig. 6, when running Leiden optimizing CPM with the smaller resolution values, as well as when optimizing modularity, all cluster types described above are evident. In all networks, most of the clusters are either degraded or reduced.

Fig 6. Cluster Fate for Leiden Clusters The fate of Leiden clusters from seven different networks as extant (not modified by CM), reduced (replaced by a smaller cluster), split (replaced by two or more smaller clusters), or degraded (replaced entirely by singletons) is indicated. Rows correspond to networks and columns correspond to clustering approach. Data are shown for CM treatment of Leiden clusters, under either CPM for 5 different resolution values or modularity. As resolution is decreased, the number of extant clusters decreases; the number of clusters that are reduced in size increases then decreases; the number of clusters that are split generally increases with the exception of modularity, which varies according to network; and the number of clusters that are degraded to singletons increases and then decreases.

Interestingly, however, in all networks, modularity optimization produces some clusters that are split, and in all but two networks, CPM-optimization with the smallest resolution value also produces some clusters that are split (this is also true for some intermediate resolution values on some networks). Thus, this study suggests that both Leiden optimizing CPM using these smaller resolution values and Leiden optimizing modularity will, for some networks, produce clusters that contain two or more valid clusters. As we noted earlier, this is a type of behavior similar to the resolution limit.

Impact of CM on IKC

We present results for both IKC on the Open Citations and CEN networks, the two largest networks out of the seven studied (Fig. 7). In comparison to Leiden, even before CM-processing, IKC-clustering has relatively low node coverage on these networks, of

20.3% and 3.8% in the case of the Open Citations and CEN networks respectively. CM treatment of these clusterings hardly impacts the node coverage for the CEN and has a small effect on node coverage on the Open Citations network. For both networks, nearly all clusters are extant and some are split, but none are reduced or degraded. Thus, IKC exhibits somewhat different response to CM than Leiden, but does also show the resolution limit behavior that we observed earlier for Leiden optimizing either modularity or CPM with small to moderate resolution parameter values.

(a) Node coverage

(b) Cluster Fate

Fig 7. Node coverage and cluster fate for IKC clusters modified by CM on the Open Citations and CEN For IKC on these two networks, node coverage is small on both the CEN and Open Citations, and slightly reduced by CM on the Open Citations network. We also see that most clusters are extant (unaffected by CM-processing) and some are split (replaced by two or more smaller clusters), but none are reduced (replaced by a single smaller cluster) or degraded (replaced by only singletons).

Impact of CM on MCL and Infomap

MCL only completed on one network (cit_hepph), and so results for MCL are limited to just that network; however, Infomap completed on all but Open Citations, so we report results on those six networks. As seen in Table 1, MCL has high initial node coverage on cit_hepph, and the impact of running CM is moderate: before CM-processing, 97.5% of the nodes are in clusters of size at least two and 69% are in clusters of size at least 11, but after CM-processing, the node coverage drops to 61.7%. Thus, while the major impact comes from the initial removal of the clusters of size at most 10 or tree clusters, there is also a reduction in node coverage as a result of finding clusters that are poorly connected.

Infomap has high initial node coverage (pre-CM) for all networks except cit_patents, and while the impact of CM-processing on node coverage depends on the network, for all networks, there is at least a moderate drop in node coverage. The smallest drop occurs for Orkut (from 100% to 84.5%), but there is a very large drop for wiki_talk (from 100% to less than 1%). For Infomap, the difference in node coverage based on clusters of size at least 2 or clusters of size at least 11 is small, so that the reduction in node coverage comes from finding and processing clusters with small edge cuts. This is consistent with the results shown in Fig. 3(b), where most of the clusters produced by Infomap were poorly connected on four of the six networks on which it ran.

A comparison between MCL and Infomap is only possible on the one cluster on which they both ran, cit_hepph. Both MCL and Infomap display high node coverage on

this network before CM-processing, but have drops in node coverage when combined with CM. However, MCL is more impacted by CM-processing than Infomap, and the pre-CM node coverage when restricted to clusters of size at least 11 is lower for MCL than for Infomap; this clearly shows that MCL made a larger number of smaller clusters than Infomap on this network. The final node coverage is also smaller for MCL than Infomap. However, with only one network analyzed by MCL in this study, it is not possible to draw any generalizable conclusions.

Table 1. Effect of CM on MCL and Infomap clustered networks

	method	network	nodes	edges	pre_nc	pre_nc10	post_nc10
1	mcl	cit_hepph	34546	420877	0.975	0.69	0.617
2	infomap	cit_hepph	34546	420877	1.0	0.996	0.707
3	infomap	cit_patents	6009555	16518947	0.628	0.626	0.114
4	infomap	orkut	3072627	117185083	1.0	1.0	0.845
5	infomap	wiki_talk	2394385	4659565	1.0	0.986	0.006
6	infomap	wiki_topcats	1791489	25444207	1.0	0.989	0.757
7	infomap	cen	14695475	92051051	0.952	0.952	0.232

nc: fraction of nodes in non-singleton clusters. pre: before CM
nc10: fraction of nodes in clusters of size > 10. post: after CM

Observations

The response to CM-processing differs between methods but also depends on the network. The dependency on the network makes sense, as some networks lend themselves to dense well-connected clusters better than others.

The variation of impact between methods is worth exploring, as while all methods show reduced node coverage as a result of CM-processing, some methods show more of a reduction. A comparison between Leiden optimizing CPM with different resolution values and optimizing modularity shows the following trends. The impact on Leiden optimizing CPM depends on the resolution value: for larger resolution values, it tends to produce extant clusters, but for the smaller resolution values it produces few extant clusters; furthermore, Leiden optimizing modularity has similar responses to CM-processing as Leiden optimizing CPM with the smallest resolution value. We note also that the pre-CM and post-CM node coverage is highest for Leiden optimizing CPM using the smallest resolution value, and lowest for CPM-optimization with the two largest resolution values. An explanation for both trends is provided by the guarantee for the minimum cut size for any CPM-optimal cluster: the lower bound increases with the resolution value r , so that when $r = 0.5$, it provides a very meaningful guarantee. Thus, the Leiden CPM variants that are the most robust to CM-processing use a very large resolution value, such as $r = 0.5$.

IKC clustering is also fairly robust to CM-processing, with generally a small reduction in node coverage, making it similar in that sense to Leiden-CPM with $r = 0.5$. It is striking to note that both of these methods have low initial node coverage in our study, reflecting that the two methods are very *conservative* in producing clusters. In contrast, most of the clustering methods we studied (e.g., Leiden-CPM with small resolution values) had high initial node coverage, reaching close to 100% in most cases, and these were the cases that were most impacted by CM-processing.

These findings suggest the possibility that in these real-world networks, only a fraction of the nodes may be in clusters that are sufficiently well-connected and sufficiently large to be considered valid, and that most clustering methods are overly aggressive in clustering – aiming for complete node coverage that may result in clusters

that are inflated. In other words, real-world networks may not be fully covered by what we consider “valid” communities, and clustering outputs may be misleading.

Clustering on Synthetic LFR networks

To evaluate the impact of CM-processing on accuracy, we generated synthetic networks using the LFR software [23]. For this experiment, we computed statistics for the Leiden clusterings of the seven real-world networks we previously explored, and used them as input to the LFR software (see Materials and Methods). We produced a collection of 34 LFR networks with ground truth communities and clustered each of these 34 LFR networks using Leiden with the same clustering parameters used to provide empirical statistics to LFR.

Fig 8. Properties of the LFR networks The top subfigure shows the node coverage (percent of each network that is covered by clusters of size at least 11) and the bottom shows the percentage of the clusters that are disconnected. Each LFR network is based on an empirical network, with cluster parameters based on Leiden optimizing modularity or CPM, with varying resolution parameters.

Properties of the LFR networks

We begin with an examination of the LFR network properties, as shown in Fig. 8. The top subfigure indicates that the LFR networks do not match the profile of node coverage exhibited in the original Leiden clustering. Second, since clusters below size 11 are filtered out, it shows that the ground truth clusters tend to be at least size 11 except in the case of LFR `cit_patents` and `wiki_topcats` networks modeled on Leiden-CPM with resolution values that are large (0.1 or 0.5). The bottom subfigure shows that the majority of the ground truth clusters for the LFR `wiki_talk` network are disconnected. Two other networks (CEN with Leiden-CPM at the two largest resolution values) also display many disconnected clusters. This further indicates that LFR has not reproduced the cluster properties for the `wiki_talk` network (as all the Leiden clusters are connected). Moreover, ground truth clusters that are disconnected suggests a larger problem with the LFR network when given the parameters for these empirical networks with their Leiden communities, as true communities should not be disconnected. Thus, these specific LFR networks with disconnected ground truth clusters are of dubious utility for evaluating community detection methods.

Impact of CM-processing on clustering accuracy

We then examined the impact of CM-processing on clustering accuracy using Normalized Mutual Information (NMI), Adjusted Rand Index (ARI), and Adjusted Mutual Information (AMI) (Fig. 9), which were calculated using the Python Scikit-Learn package [24]. Since most of the LFR `wiki_talk` network ground truth clusters are disconnected, we do not consider accuracy on this network to be a valid evaluation. Similarly, most of the ground truth clusters for the CEN network based on CPM-optimization with resolution parameters 0.1 and 0.5 are disconnected, and we also do not consider accuracy on those networks to be worth considering. Our focus thus turns to the impact of CM processing on the remaining networks.

Interpreting the impact of CM-processing on clustering accuracy depends, to some extent, on which of the three cluster criteria are considered. However, for all three criteria, when restricted to the networks that do not have a majority of disconnected clusters, CM usually improves or maintains accuracy. CM produces a large improvement in accuracy when applied to the networks based on Leiden-modularity or Leiden-CPM with small resolution values. The two conditions where CM hurts accuracy are `cit_patents` and `wiki_topcats` for CPM-optimization with $r = 0.1$ (i.e., a large resolution value). Those are two model conditions where most ground truth clusters are at most size 10 (as evidenced by the low node coverage), which has the result that CM removes those clusters. The explanation for the reduction in accuracy is that CM removes clusters that are that small, and this can result in a decrease in accuracy when many ground truth clusters are small. Interestingly, there are other conditions with small node coverage (indicating many ground truth clusters are below size 11) where CM does not reduce accuracy. CM also shows a small decrease in accuracy under AMI for the `cit_hepph` network when used with CPM-optimization and resolution value $r = 0.1$, and this is a condition that is not characterized by small ground truth clusters or many disconnected clusters. Thus, in general CM can be beneficial when used on networks that do not have a large number of disconnected clusters or clusters that are below its threshold of 11.

Evaluating how well LFR networks resemble the empirical networks and clusterings

In this study, we used LFR networks to evaluate accuracy for different clustering methods, as well as to explore the impact of using CM-processing on this accuracy.

Fig 9. Impact of CM-processing on clustering accuracy on LFR networks. The panels show accuracy measured in terms of NMI (top), AMI (middle) and ARI (bottom), with respect to the LFR ground-truth communities. Each condition on the x-axis corresponds to a *different* LFR network, generated to reproduce the empirical properties of a Leiden-modularity or Leiden-CPM clustering with a given resolution parameter. In total, there are 34 different LFR networks. In most conditions, CM improves the accuracy of the original Leiden clustering, except for some of the conditions (Fig. 8) when the ground-truth communities have many (at least 60%) disconnected clusters, or the node coverage by clusters of size at least 11 is low (at most 70%).

Here we examine the question of how well these LFR networks resemble the real-world networks and the clusterings of the networks we computed using Leiden.

As provided in the supplementary materials, empirical statistics such as average node degree, the mixing parameter, and exponents for the power-law distributions for vertex degrees and community sizes in the LFR networks are very close to the statistics for the associated real-world networks. Yet, a more careful examination of the node degree distributions and community size distributions (supplementary materials) show that they are very different in their tails. Furthermore, as we observed in Fig. 8, some of the LFR networks we generated using the LFR software had disconnected clusters.

Given that all the communities we used to define the LFR networks are computed by Leiden, and hence are guaranteed to be connected [8], this is another significant way in which LFR can produce ground truth clusters that do not match the features of the clustering of the associated real-world network. These differences between LFR and the real-world networks and communities on which they are based indicate that accuracy on LFR networks *may not* be predictive of accuracy on real-world networks, and suggests a need for improved tools to generate networks with ground-truth community structure that more closely replicates the features of real-world networks.

Conclusion

We argue that communities should be both dense and well-connected and that these two properties are separable. Using seven real-world networks ranging in size from tens of thousands to tens of millions of nodes and five clustering methods, we report that each of the tested methods produce clusters that do not meet a mild standard for well-connectedness. The failure to meet even a mild standard for connectivity suggests a limitation of the methods tested. However, we used only seven real world networks in our study, and studying additional networks and testing more methods will be informative.

Since many clustering methods aim to maximize node coverage, weakly connected parts of a network may be merged into communities that subsequently fail even modest standards for connectivity. Thus, a user must consider a trade-off between node coverage and well-connectedness when exploring community structure. However, a universal standard for connectivity does not exist and may not even be useful. For this reason, CM was designed to allow the user to set a discriminating threshold for well-connected that would depend on the context of the investigation, the network, the clustering algorithm used, parameter settings, and the purpose of a study.

CM enables users to assess the clusters returned by community detection methods and modify them. The extent to which CM-processing changes a given clustering varies according to the input network, the choice of clustering algorithm and its algorithmic parameters such as the resolution parameter for CPM-optimization, and the well-connectedness criterion, all of which can be specified by the user.

Results from this study suggest the possibility that portions of real world networks may not exhibit community structure. A related study addresses whether a graph can be considered clusterable and describes a test for this purpose [19]. Thus, complementary approaches to address the question of clusterability include methods that have the ability to estimate clusterability and to identify the clusterable portions of a network *prior* to clustering (as opposed to in a post-clustering framework, which is what CM does). Furthermore, methods that inherently ensure well-connectedness based on a user-specified criterion would be valuable.

That LFR networks produce different patterns than empirical networks is not surprising. An assumption underlying the methodology is that the degree distribution and cluster size distributions follow a power law, and it is known that the power-law

may not fit many real-world networks well [25–28]. In our study, we observed that degree distribution and cluster size distributions were imperfectly fitted by LFR software in some cases.

In addition, the assumption in the LFR model that every node is in a community can be questioned, as it can result, for some parameter settings, in “ground truth” communities that are poorly connected or even disconnected. In this regard, we are interested in newer models, such as *ABCD_o* [29], which include outlier nodes that are not in any community, as these may offer value.

It is also important to be able to distinguish between the existence of a community and whether it can be detected. Excessive emphasis on well-connected clusters may result in a reduced detection and incomplete descriptions of communities. Additionally, informative weaker links [30] may be lost, since CM may remove such edges although they would remain in the input graph. On the other hand, well-connected communities could be useful in defining core meso-scale structures with additional discovery made through relaxing the user-specified criterion. Future work should also incorporate evaluation criteria relevant to the input network.

Materials and Methods

Real world networks

Table 2. Real world networks used in this study

network	# nodes	# edges	average_node_deg	reference
Open Citations	75,025,194	1,363,303,678	36.34	[20]
CEN	13,989,436	92,051,051	13.16	[31]
cit_hepph	34,546	420,877	24.37	[32]
cit_patents	3,774,768	16,518,947	8.75	[32]
orkut	3,072,441	117,185,083	76.28	[33]
wiki_talk	2,394,385	4,659,565	3.89	[34]
wiki_topcats	1,791,489	25,444,207	28.41	[35]

The publicly available Open Citations dataset was downloaded in Aug 2022, parsed into a PostgreSQL database, curated, and annotated with integer identifiers for each DOI [36]. The CEN is a citation network constructed from the literature on exosome research. From the SNAP repository, we downloaded *cit_hepph*, a High Energy Physics citation network; *cit_patents*, a citation network of US patents; *orkut*, a social media network; *wiki_talk*, a network containing users and discussion from the inception of Wikipedia until January 2008; and *wiki_topcats*, a web graph of Wikimedia hyperlinks. All networks were processed to remove self-loops, duplicate edges, and parallel edges before clustering.

LFR networks

In order to evaluate accuracy, we need networks with ground truth communities. Thus, we generated synthetic networks with known community structure to provide this capability. We used the LFR software [23, 37], for this purpose, which requires the following parameters:

- Network properties: The simulator requires information about the degree distribution of the network (assumed to be a power law), provided by the average k and maximum k_{max} vertex degrees, and the negative exponent for degree sequence (τ_1). It also requires the number N of nodes.

- Community properties: The simulator requires information about the cluster size distribution, provided by the maximum and minimum community sizes (c_{max} and c_{min}), and the negative exponent for the community size distribution (τ_2).
- Mixing parameter μ : The simulator also requires this value, which is the ratio between the number of neighbors of a vertex that are not in the same community, to the total number of neighbors of the vertex, averaged over all vertices.

We used the empirical networks to produce LFR networks. The empirical networks directly provide the network properties, but the community properties and mixing parameter values depend on the given clustering. Therefore, for each of the empirical networks, we also considered the Leiden clusterings, produced either using modularity optimization or CPM-optimization with varying resolution parameters. For each combination of empirical network and Leiden clustering, we estimated the community properties. We used *networkX* [38,39] to compute the number of nodes and average and maximum node degrees. For the negative exponent for the two power law distributions, we used the approach from [40] that is implemented in the *powerlaw* Python package [41]. Since the power-law property may not hold for the whole distribution, following [40], we estimated x_{min} , the minimum value for which the power-law property holds as well as the exponent α for the tail of the distribution. We wrote a custom script to estimate the mixing parameter, μ .

We then gave the required parameters (network properties, community properties, and mixing parameter) to the LFR software [23]. We observed scalability limitations of the software [42] when trying to simulate very large networks, corresponding to the Open Citations network and CEN. Therefore, for any network with more than 10 million nodes, we simulated networks with only 3 million nodes, using modified network and community property parameters (i.e., preserving average degree and mixing parameter). We also found that for the LFR network simulator to converge, we had to modify the ranges of the community sizes, i.e., increase c_{min} and decrease c_{max} . As shown in the statistics reported in the supplementary materials, this protocol produced LFR networks that had very good fit to the empirical statistics (i.e., the average node degree, the mixing parameter, and the exponents for the degree and community size distributions) of the associated empirical network. Furthermore, except for the LFR networks simulated for the CEN and Open Citations network, the LFR networks had the same number of nodes as the corresponding empirical network.

The Connectivity Modifier Pipeline

To remediate poorly-connected clusters, we developed a modular pipeline that we now describe (Fig. 4). By design, this pipeline is guaranteed to return a clustering where each cluster is well-connected according to the function $f(n)$ and has size at least B . The values of $f(n)$ and B used in this study are set as default but can be easily modified by a user. Note that if an input cluster meets these two criteria, it will be present in the output clustering. Furthermore, every cluster in the output will either be one of the input clusters or will be a subset of one of the input clusters.

The CM pipeline requires the user to specify values for three algorithmic parameters:

- B , the minimum allowed size of any “valid” vertex community (default $B = 11$)
- $f(n)$, so that a cluster is considered well-connected if and only if its min cut size exceeds $f(n)$ (default: $f(n) = \log_{10} n$); we require $f(n) \geq 1$ for all n , and that $f(n)$ be an increasing function.
- A clustering method; the current implementation allows for Leiden optimizing CPM, Leiden optimizing modularity, the Iterative k-core (IKC) method with

$k = 10$, MCL, and Infomap. Support for additional methods is in active development. 547
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The input to the CM pipeline is a network \mathcal{G} with N nodes and the algorithmic parameters as specified. The pipeline then operates in four stages: 549
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- Stage 1: A clustering is generated from the input network \mathcal{G} . 551
- Stage 2: The clustering is filtered to remove clusters below size B and all trees since trees can be split into two parts by deleting a single edge, are are therefore not well-connected for any size, according to our framework. 552
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- Stage 3: The Connectivity Modifier (CM) is applied to each cluster that remains. First, all nodes of degree at most $f(n)$ are removed (where n is the number of nodes in the cluster), until there are no low degree nodes remaining. Then, for each remaining cluster, a min cut is calculated using VieCut [22], and if it is not greater than $f(n)$ in size then the min cut is removed, thus splitting the cluster into two components. These components are then re-clustered using the selected clustering method, and the process repeats until all clusters are well-connected. 555
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- Stage 4: Any resultant clusters below size B are removed. 562

Supporting information 563

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